

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SPEECH PRODUCTION AND PERSONALITY

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Abstract. This paper explores the relationship between speech production and personality. It analyzes two personality traits – extroversion and introversion and their effects on speech clarity and speed and how students with such personalities achieve academic performance. The study is based on previous psychological and linguistic research, which suggests that personality role is significant in second language acquisition and oral communication.

Keywords: speech production, extraversion, introversion, fluency, anxiety, oral communication, short-term memory, long-term recall, memory capacity, confidence.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola nutq hosil qilish va shaxsiyat o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni o'rganadi. Unda ikki xil shaxsiy xususiyat – ekstraversiya va introversiya – hamda ularning nutqning aniqligi va tezligiga ta'siri, shuningdek, bunday shaxsiyatga ega talabalar qanday akademik natijalarga erishishi tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot avvalgi psixologik va lingvistik izlanishlarga asoslanadi va ular shaxsiyatning ikkinchi tilni o'zlashtirish hamda og'zaki muloqotdagi roli muhim ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: nutq hosil qilish, ekstraversiya, introversiya, ravonlik, xavotir, og'zaki muloqot, qisqa muddatli xotira, uzoq muddatli eslab qolish, xotira sig'imi, o'ziga ishonch.

Аннотация. Данная статья рассматривает взаимосвязь между рождением речи и личностными особенностями. В ней анализируются два типа личности – экстраверсия и интроверсия – их влияние на ясность и скорость речи, а также то, как студенты с такими личностными характеристиками достигают академических результатов. Исследование основано на предыдущих психологических и лингвистических работах, которые показывают, что роль личности является значимой в усвоении второго языка и устной коммуникации.

Ключевые слова: речевое производство, экстраверсия, интроверсия, беглость речи, тревожность, устное общение, кратковременная память, долговременная память, объем памяти, уверенность.

Introduction

Communication is becoming an important part of our everyday lives. To achieve success both professionally and academically, fluent and confident speech is needed. Without it, the majority of people face difficulties in terms of finding an appropriate job and performing better in educational institutions such as schools and universities. However, speech production not only depends on knowledge, but is closely linked to personality traits. This paper aims to explore the role of personality when producing speech and to investigate the results of different students' academic performances.

People are usually divided into two groups: extroverts and introverts. Individuals with these personality traits share various characteristics and brain functions. Extroverts are superior in speech production because of their brain functioning. They have a short-term memory and an ability to show a better performance under stress and less vulnerable to anxiety, resulting in better verbal communication. (Dewaele and Furnham 1999; Howarth and Eysenck 1968). Psychological studies show that extraverts are better at communication skills, which require short-term recall, while introverts have long-term recall, which is beneficial in written tasks (Dewaele and Furnham 1999; Howarth and Eysenck 1968). Dewaele and Furnham assumed that extroverted people are more likely to perform better in periods when oral production is required compared to producing written output.

Another study also investigates and proves the connection between foreign language learning and personality traits including extraversion. Busch (1982) analyzed the connection between extraversion and introversion and EFL proficiency among Japanese learners, including junior and adult college students by giving standardized English proficiency tests and oral interviews. The analysis revealed that top scores on the grammar and reading sections of this test were observed among introverts. In contrast, extroverted college students showed a strong performance in oral interviews. This investigation showed that both personality types have enough linguistic knowledge and better understanding in L2, but performance is different depending on task type, with extraverts being skilled in verbal communication and introverts being better in receptive skills.

Unlike extraverts, introverts possess completely different personality traits. They are usually anxious (Cheek & Buss, 1981) and high levels of anxiety in introverts reduce attention and limit brain capacity. (Fremont et al., 1976, Eysenck, 1979; M.W. Eysenck, 1981). Eysenck suggested that anxious people's attention is not fully given to the one important thing. This is mainly because their attention is divided into two parts: doing the task and self-perception, reducing the working memory capacity, which, in turn, leads to less productive cognitive performance. MacIntyre and Charos (1996) found that introverts do not have a strong desire to communicate in their L2 compared to extraverts. These findings show that extraverts achieve a higher level of fluency in L2 language and speak spontaneously, whereas introverts suffer from hesitation and pauses when speaking in L2 language making them less fluent.

Conclusion

In conclusion, speech production is closely related to personality traits, particularly extraversion and introversion. Extroverted individuals usually perform better in oral communication as they have lower anxiety, greater confidence, which lead to more fluent speech. In contrast, while introverts often perform better in tasks that require accuracy, such as reading and grammar, they may experience a higher level of anxiety in speaking. However, introverted individuals also might achieve fluency by practicing a lot and working on themselves over time.

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